

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

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1st Report on national needs

WP 2 – T2.3

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¹ PU = Public

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Abstract

The National Hubs (NHs) established in PARC are crucial building blocks of the Partnership as they play a key role in sharing information and needs in a two-way dialogue between the partnership players and the national stakeholders. PARC supports the continuous development of the NHs; thus, a peer-to-peer learning process was developed to foster the sustainable development of the NHs from the beginning of the Partnership. An online survey was developed and launched in the first year of PARC (i) to develop a baseline for the NHs; (ii) to identify the existing knowledge gaps, requests, suggestions and expertise and (iii) to address some specific requests arising from the Work Packages (WPs).

Based on the responses of the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) more than 50% of the NHs were built on the NHs established in the HBM4EU project and involved from 2 to 9 different types of organizations. Most of the PARC activities were covered by experts in the NHs; however, about two thirds of the NHs were lacking expertise in FAIR data. Regarding the implementation of NHs, the lack of funding for organizing NH meetings, difficulties in defining the agenda of the meeting and keeping the members active and engaged were identified as challenges.

All NHCPs mentioned that they would like to receive information on the expected requests formulated to help the progress of the implementation of PARC activities by the WPs in advance and some of them highlighted that more time to complete the surveys and short meetings to better understand the requests on specific topics are needed. The NHCPs formulated several requests towards the different PARC groups such as the need for frequent information sharing, communication materials and stronger engagement of the leaders of the different WPs and tasks.

The 1st NHCP face-to-face meeting was organized in Riga, Latvia on 26-27 April 2023 to discuss, among others, the further needs of the NHs.

Based on the results of the first survey for mapping the needs of the NHs and the needs reported by the NHCPs during the 1st NHCP meeting, recommendations were formulated on (i) the communication within the NHCP network and capacity building, (ii) communication within PARC and (iii) optimisation of the input from the NHCPs and NHs. The recommendations to reflect on the needs are described in detail in this deliverable.

Key Words

national hub, national needs, network, survey, sustainability

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Authors and acknowledgements

The authors are listed in the technical reference table. The contribution of all T2.3 partners to the development of the survey is thanked. INSA prepared the survey in REDCap. The authors would like to hereby acknowledge the cooperation of the National Hub Contact Points who completed the survey and provided valuable inputs during the face-to-face meeting.

Acronyms

GB: Governing Board

HBM4EU: Human Biomonitoring for EU project, co-funded under Horizon 2020

NGO: Non-Governmental Organization

NH: National Hub

NHC: National Hub Coordinator

NHCP: National Hub Contact Point

SSbD: Safe and Sustainable by Design

TL: Task co-leaders

WP: Work Package

WPL: WP co-leader

1. Introduction

Lessons learnt under HMB4EU (a project co-funded under Horizon 2020 aimed at coordinating and advancing human biomonitoring in Europe; Kolossa-Gehring et al. 2023), have been integrated into PARC. Furthermore, many participating organizations in HMB4EU are also partners in PARC (Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals), and the Partnership benefits from experience of organization of a National Hub (NH) in each participating country as already done in HMB4EU. The construction of a NH is based on country needs, there are no prescriptive rules to the structure or activities of the NHs. They are networks of organizations at the country level, involving PARC partners, the relevant national ministries and public and research institutions and other stakeholders (e.g. industries, NGOs, trade unions) active in the field of chemical risk assessment outside the umbrella of PARC as well. Each country has a designated National Hub Contact Point (NHCP) who coordinates the exchange nationally and contributes to the development of synergies with related national/EU initiatives. The NHs are crucial building blocks of the Partnership, essential for the fulfilment and sustainability of the main PARC activities. PARC is co-funded from national resources, which shows the importance of the NHs. Stable NHs play a key role in sharing information and needs in a two-way dialogue between the partnership players and the national stakeholders.

Thus, the continuous development of the NHs is a key action in PARC and a peer-to-peer learning process is being developed to foster the sustainable development of the NHs from the beginning of the Partnership. This process is coordinated by the National Hub Coordinators (NHCs) based on the inputs of the NHCPs and supported by the PARC's T2.3 'Sustainability' partners. To develop a baseline for PARC NHs and to identify the existing knowledge gaps, requests, suggestions and expertise, a survey was developed and launched in the first year of PARC. The survey was used to respond to certain specific requests arising from the Work Packages (WPs) to help the progress of the implementation of PARC activities.

Furthermore, annual surveys will be sent to the NHs to track the progress and regularly get feedback and suggestions through the NHCPs. Besides the annual surveys, the needs of the NHs are collected and discussed during the annual meetings of the NHCPs. A first meeting took place on 26-27 April 2023 in Riga, Latvia. The aims of this first face-to-face meeting were to (i) meet NHCPs and start to establish the network; (ii) report on activities carried out in the first year; (iii) discuss structures, plans, needs, expectations of NHs/NHCPs.

The outcomes of the surveys and annual meetings will be used to promote the development of the NHs by providing solutions for their needs (e.g. developing materials) and transposing some of them to training and capacity building programmes in WP9 'Building infrastructural and human capacities'. The results will also be used within the scope of the follow-up of the indicator framework developed in PARC to provide inputs on the outputs, outcomes and impacts achieved in PARC. The mapping of needs of NHs is a living process and will continue the entire duration of the Partnership.

This report contains the results of the 1st survey for mapping the needs of the NHs and the outcomes of the first meeting of the NHCPs. Furthermore, some recommendations are formulated based on the reported needs.

2. Methods

2.1 Implementation of the 1st survey for mapping the needs of the NHs

The first survey for mapping the needs of the NHs was composed of 16 questions organized in three sections. The first section, to be completed solely by the NHCPs, aimed to identify the NH baseline in PARC and contained questions on the structure and operation of the NHs, including their composition and the actions and activities planned in the NH as well as the identification of any difficulties in the setting up of the NHs and their implementation. This section also aimed to share the first experiences of the NHs and suggestions for collecting their input in PARC and how to support them.

The second section of the survey was dedicated to topic specific questions on communication activities and preliminary ideas on the sustainability of PARC-related activities. These questions were designed to be discussed in the NHs and the response compiled for the NH by the NHCP. The questionnaire is available in Annex I.

Further to discussions with WP9 and in particular Task 9.4 on Training, it appeared necessary, in the same timeframe, to capture training needs from all the NH members on PARC-related scientific topics in order to help strategically prioritize training(s) to be carried out up in the first period of PARC. Therefore, a link to the first online survey on training needs (developed by T9.4 'Training' partners) to be completed by all NH members was also integrated into the survey for mapping the needs of the NHs.

The online survey for mapping the needs of the NHs was created in REDCap and launched on 21 December 2022. It was sent to all PARC NHs through their NHCPs for completion by 31 January 2023. In light of the holiday period and the importance of setting a baseline through this first survey and hence trying to get as many responses as possible, the deadline was later extended to 14 February 2023. The results were exported and analysed in Microsoft Excel.

2.2 Organization of the 1st face-to-face PARC NHCP meeting

The first meeting of the NHCPs took place in Riga, Latvia on 26-27 April 2023. The event was hosted by Rīga Stradiņš University Medical Education and Technology Center. There were 23 countries participating in the meeting.

The programme of the event started with a welcome from the representatives of the host institution and the PARC coordinator, followed by an introductory session clarifying the aims and topics of the 2-day-meeting. Further activities consisted of plenary sessions presenting results of the two surveys mentioned above (mapping the needs of the NHs and training needs) and breakout sessions to present and discuss (i) indicators of success of the NH, (ii) communication and dissemination between the NHCP, WP or tasks in PARC and the NHCs, and (iii) sustainability of the NHs.

During the final session on Day 2, the NHCPs were split into two groups and each NHCP gave a brief presentation of their current NH structure (involved institutions, expertise covered by the members), ongoing activities as well as their plans and needs at the national level.

Finally, there was a discussion on the future expectations from the NHCP meetings and their organization (either face-to-face or virtual online meetings).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Results of the 1st survey for mapping the needs of the NHs

The survey was completed for 25 out of the 28 countries participating in PARC. These countries were the following: Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Hungary, Germany, Iceland, Israel, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxemburg, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Slovakia, Slovenia, and United Kingdom. No response was submitted by Greece, Italy and the Netherlands.

Feedback from Section 1 of the survey: Questions on the structure, operation and the first experiences of the NHs

General information on the NHs and their establishment (questions 1 to 4)

Almost all countries have established a NH at the end of January 2023, except for Israel and Poland. The size of the NHs varies significantly among the countries; the smallest NHs include only 2 organizations, while more than 30 organizations are involved in the largest NHs (Fig. 1). In total, 363 organizations are involved in the PARC NH network. Several NHCPs mentioned that their NH is expected to continue expanding until the end of the first year of PARC (May 2023).

Fig. 1. Size of the NHs (*countries planning to expand the NH with other organisations before May 2023)

Fig. 2. shows a summary of the members of NHs. The organizations participating in PARC activities (including the Beneficiaries and the Affiliated Entities (AEs)) were mentioned by all NHCPs. The Governing Board (GB) member organizations were also included in all NHs except for one country. In approximately half of the countries, scientists, policy makers and regulators other than those involved in PARC are already engaged in the NHs. National Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and representatives from the industry are also included in approximately one third of the NHs. Furthermore, a few NHs already have

members from consumer associations, trade unions and other types of organizations. The NHs involve from 2 to 9 different types of organizations with a median value of 5.

Fig. 2. Involvement of different stakeholders in the NHs

The PARC activities cover a wide range of topics, and requests towards the NHs are expected from various fields; thus, we mapped the expertise of the NH members, and the summary of the results is depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Expertise covered by the NH members

Experts in human biomonitoring, environmental and multisource monitoring and risk assessment were reported for almost all NHs. Experts in occupational exposure, hazard assessment and communication

and dissemination were involved in more than half of the NHs, while about two thirds of the NHs were lacking expertise in FAIR data.

The results highlight that many of the NHs would benefit from the inclusion of additional stakeholders and expertise (e.g. data experts).

Based on the results of the survey, **13 out of the 23 NHs** (which is more than 50%) **were built on the NHs established in the framework of the HBM4EU project**, but not all of the institutes which took a lead as NHCP were the same. It must be noted that all countries involved in PARC had representatives in the HBM4EU consortium,

The NHs are intersectoral groups including different types of organizations and covering a wide range of expertise. We asked the NHCPs in the survey whether there are any intersectoral groups in their countries which were established to discuss national priorities and activities on chemical risk assessment or not.

According to the knowledge of the NHCPs, **15 countries had already established intersectoral groups focusing on chemical risk assessment**. These include groups varying in structure, topics covered and the number of member organizations. Some examples include the Toxicological Council in Sweden, Flemish coordination hub on chemicals of high concern, Finland's advisory committee on chemicals, Intergovernmental Group on Health Risks from Chemicals in the United Kingdom, Forum coordinated by the Norwegian Environment Agency or the Governmental Intersectoral Commission for Chemical Safety in Slovenia. In a couple of cases, more than one group covers the different aspects of chemical risk assessment.

PARC can be a pioneer in creating a platform and bringing together the different stakeholders working in the field of chemical risk assessment in certain countries as there are several countries where, based on the knowledge of the NHCP, there is a lack of intersectoral groups to discuss national priorities and activities on chemical risk assessment.

The NHCPs reported that they did not have any difficulties in identifying the potential members of the NH, except for two countries. Lack of time for searching and lack of information on what certain organizations are focusing on were mentioned as difficulties.

However, **5 NHCPs mentioned that they have difficulties in engaging stakeholders, mainly policy makers and regulators**. Almost half of the NHCPs have not contacted all potential NH members yet.

Information on the implementation of NHs and their activities (questions 5 to 8)

The NHCPs were asked to describe the NH activities they were planning to implement in the first year of PARC (Fig. 4). **Almost all NHCPs mentioned the organization of NH meetings. Furthermore, about one third of the NHCPs mentioned the establishment of a dedicated platform for sharing documents and other materials with the NH members.** Moreover, some NHCPs also planned to implement specific communication and dissemination activities such as conferences, webinars or seminars and developing communication materials.

Fig. 4. Planned NH activities in the first year of PARC

More than half of the NHCPs were planning to organize 2 or 3 NH meetings in the first year of PARC, while only one meeting was scheduled for the first year in 10 countries (Fig. 5). There is only one country where more than 3 meetings were planned.

Fig. 5. Distribution of the number of NH meetings planned by the NHCPs in the first year of PARC

We asked the NHCPs in the survey whether they plan to invite all NH members to each NH meeting, or if the list of invited partners depends on the agenda of the meeting. Based on the responses, **half of the**

NHCPs are going to invite all NH members to each meeting, while an invitation based on the agenda of the meeting was preferred by the other half of the respondents (Fig. 6). There was no association between the size of the NH and the preferred approach.

Fig. 6. Distribution of the preferred approaches for the invitation of the members to the NH meetings

The NHCPs were asked to describe existing or potential problems that they were facing with regard to the organization of the NH meetings.

- Problems were not reported by about one third of the NHCPs.
- Seven NHCPs mentioned that **a dedicated budget would facilitate the organization of the NH meetings.**
- The same number of NHCPs indicated that **they have difficulties in defining the agenda of the meetings and keeping the NH members active and engaged** until the end of the project.
- A couple of NHCPs mentioned that the **NH members are usually very busy**, and it is difficult for them to participate in the NH meetings.

Suggestions for support and optimization of the collection of inputs from NHs (questions 9 to 12)

Several requests on various fields (e.g. data collection at national level, identifying stakeholders for certain tasks, etc.) will be formulated by the different WPs towards the NHs during the project. The NHCPs play a crucial role in managing these requests. We asked the NHCPs about the preferred approaches for receiving requests from the different PARC groups and the results are summarized in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Distribution of the preferred approaches for receiving requests from the different PARC groups

All NHCPs mentioned that they would like to receive information on the expected requests in advance as this could facilitate the better handling of the requests. Furthermore, half of the NHCPs indicated that they would like to receive each request in a separate e-mail, while receiving several requests at the same time was preferred by the other half of the respondents.

Several suggestions were formulated by the NHCPs on how to facilitate the handling of the requests.

- Almost one third of the respondents mentioned that a **calendar including all upcoming requests would be highly appreciated** as this could help the planning of the NH meetings.
- Some NHCPs noted that **more time is needed to complete the surveys**.
- A couple of NHCPs mentioned that an **explanation on what the requested information will be used for** would be useful as well as **short meetings to better understand the requests on specific topics** are needed to facilitate the completion of the surveys. On the other hand, there are NHCPs who would prefer **short and clear e-mails**.
- The use of **networking tools** to facilitate interactions and sending **deadline alerts** were also noted.

Information was collected on how the NHCPs are going to collect inputs from the NH members for requests from the different WPs that require input by all NH members. The three most preferred approaches were the following: contacting the relevant NH members directly, organizing a NH meeting and forwarding the request to all NH members (Fig. 8). A few NHCPs mentioned that they will try to answer the request themselves without contacting the members of the NH.

Fig. 8. Distribution of the preferred approaches for collecting inputs from the NH members for requests

Besides the NHCs, there are several internal PARC bodies aiming to support the development of the NHs. We asked the opinion of the NHCPs on how the different PARC bodies could support the national actions that the NHCPs would like to implement.

The NHCPs formulated several requests towards the different PARC groups.

- Almost all NHCPs mentioned that **frequent information sharing is needed**. The NHCPs would like to receive **regular updates on the past, recent and planned PARC activities and events** which might be relevant for the NHs. On the other hand, **sharing good practices on the operation of the NHs among the NHCPs would be very useful** for them, especially in the countries which do not have consolidated NHs. It was highlighted that the NHCs should identify the best practices regarding the structure, organization and actions taken by the NHCPs and share this within the network of the NHCPs.
- For the engagement of the different stakeholders, the **need for communication materials** was also mentioned by several NHCPs. General and targeted materials were also listed.
- Some NHCPs mentioned that **stronger engagement of the WPLs and Task co-Leaders (TLs) should be achieved**. The NHCPs expect to receive a notice in advance about the requests formulated by the different WPs and to be informed about the possibilities of participation in future PARC activities. A couple of NHCPs mentioned that it would be useful if WPLs or TLs could participate in NH meetings and talk about their work. Moreover, it was mentioned that WPL and TLs should be informed about the NHs to inspire them on how the structure of NHs can be used to support the objectives of the WPs and tasks as effectively as possible. It was noted that the WPLs and TLs should be open to the suggestions and needs of the NHs.

Feedback from section 2: Topic specific questions related to the mapping of needs of the NHs

This concerns only the questions on communication activities (questions 1 to 3)

The NHCPs play an important role in sharing the knowledge generated in PARC at national level. This can be done in several ways, like sharing information on the website of their institutes. Based on the results of the survey, **most of the NHCPs mentioned that either the NHCP institute or other NH member institute(s) will have a dedicated section about PARC on their website** (Fig.9). In six countries, more than one institute is planning to have a dedicated section on PARC on their institute’s website. However, several other countries indicated that they are not planning to create a dedicated section about PARC on the NHCP’s website or any of their NH members’ websites but only some news related to PARC will be shared on their websites.

Fig. 9. Information on how the NH members will share information about PARC on their websites

Several communication products (e.g., leaflets, policy briefs, research briefs, factsheets, infographics, videos, newsletters) will be developed in PARC in English. We asked the NHCPs to prioritize which communication materials would benefit being translated into national languages. The results are depicted in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Prioritisation of communication materials based on the need for translation in national languages

It is clear from the answers that **the NHCPs would like to receive several different communication materials in national languages**. They consider PARC factsheets and leaflets as the most important products.

The translation of many communication materials to all languages is expensive; thus, we asked the NHCPs about their willingness to translate communication materials, if resources could be allocated. In total 18 NHCPs mentioned that they are willing to do the translation. In the case of the UK, this question was not relevant, while in other cases the willingness is low.

3.2. Needs reported by the NHCPs during the 1st NHCP meeting

The key messages from the 1st NHCP meeting were that the foundation of the NHs has been established in all PARC countries. As about 50% of the NHs have been built on from the NHs started in HBM4EU, there is a considerable amount of expertise in human biomonitoring, with environmental (multisource) monitoring and risk assessment in many of the NHs to match the objectives of PARC. The main gap in expertise was on FAIR data, and the safe and sustainable by design (SSbD). The main finding is that the NHs are active in organising meetings and looking to expand their capabilities in the years to come.

Regarding the needs of the NHs - besides some specific needs addressed - there were several needs and issues identified by the majority of the NHCPs.

In general, **there is a need for sustainable funding at the national level** and to ensure that the co-funding for PARC is stable during the entire duration of the project. Many NHCPs are looking to secure additional funding which could be used for specific activities in PARC (e.g., surveys of exposure) or for participating in new activities / projects.

There is a need to ensure that **the ‘voice’ of the NHs is recognized and represented in the governance of PARC**. This is an issue that should be addressed to the GB and / or the Grant Signatory Board, where representation of these boards should also be in the NHs. This is something that could be explored further.

There was an extensive discussion regarding the communication channels between PARC groups (WP or TLs) and NHCPs. This should be done via the NHCs as this would allow both coordination and efficiency in the requests being made. Efforts to streamline this in the coming year is being made by the NHCs and the T2.3 co-leaders. Virtual meetings to design surveys and collate requests to the NHCPs are planned, and a timeline of the upcoming requests and surveys from the WP and TLs to NHCPs will be prepared.

All NHCPs expressed the need to receive feedback on the use of their national inputs and responses to specific surveys and other queries in PARC. This information is important to keep NHs active and focused on the PARC activities and at the same time, it will convince the NHs that their input is important. The results can be reported during NHCP meetings as presentations or in the form of short reports sent electronically.

NHCPs are eager to present their NHs at the consortium meeting and at the same time, members of the NHs would appreciate their participation at the PARC consortium meetings.

3.3. Recommendations

Based on the results of the first survey for mapping the needs of the NHs and the needs reported by the NHCPs during the 1st NHCP meeting, the following recommendations can be formulated:

Communication within the NHCP network and capacity building

- There are several requests and identified needs which require discussions within the network of the NHCPs; thus, **besides the annual NHCP meetings, additional (online) meetings are necessary.**
- NHCPs highlighted their need for support on how to **engage stakeholders**, mainly policy makers, regulators and other groups with low representation (e.g. NGOS, representatives from the industry, trade unions) in the NHs as well as for **sharing good practices on the operation** (structure, organization, actions taken) of the NHs. The NHCPs also mentioned the lack of financial resources for organizing NH meetings; thus, **discussions on how PARC could support the NHCPs for the organization of the NH meetings would be useful.** Concerning the resources, due to the nature of the partnership, PARC cannot cover only national activities, however the Person-Months (PMs) for organizing and participating in NH meetings are eligible costs for PARC participating organizations. Discussions on how to create a win-win situation for the NHCPs and NH members to stimulate and valorise their input and ensure useful output is also provided to them from their participation in the NHs may help in this respect. Also, the engagement of the PARC GB members in the NHs is important, as they bring in the political (and financial) commitment and notably ensure alignment of PARC activities with activities undertaken at the national level. Thus, **good practices should be shared by the NHCPs coordinating consolidated NHs with the other NHCPs.**
- Members of the NHs have the expertise to cover most of the main activities of PARC except for expertise in the FAIR data domain. Thus, it is clear that **training is needed in the field of FAIR data to increase national capacities.**
- **Several communication materials** targeting the general public and other stakeholders **will be developed in PARC which might support the NHCPs to foster the engagement of the different stakeholders.** Further discussions are needed to define which materials would benefit from being translated into national languages. **Support from WP3 'Synergies, collaborations and awareness' would also be useful on this topic.**

Communication within PARC

- The NHCPs would like to receive regular updates on the past, recent and planned PARC activities and events which might be relevant for the NHs. After the deadline for the completion of the survey, **the PARC website and the social media channels were established and regularly updated with news and events**. Furthermore, **the PARC newsletters**, the Science Digest (monthly) and the PARC Sampler (twice a year), **also provide information on the latest PARC activities**. NHCPs should be **encouraged to sign up to receive these newsletters** and should also encourage their NH members to do so.
- **More regular communication with the WPLs should be implemented** to provide information to the NHCPs about the possibilities of participation in future PARC activities.

Optimisation of the input from the NHCPs and NHs

- Several requests have already been formulated by the different WPs; thus, the **coordination of the requests sent to the NHCPs** is crucial as the NHCPs have limited resources to handle them.
- The NHCs and the T2.3 co-leaders organized bilateral meetings with the leaders of each WP in the first year of PARC to discuss their needs and expectations from the NHs. In some cases, the WPLs had high expectations; thus, **reviewing the requests of the WPLs is an important step** in the process **which should be regularly done by the NHCs with the support of T2.3**.
- Furthermore, **better structured requests** would be useful for the NHCPs. Official requests to the NHCPs and NHs should only be sent by the NHCs or the PARC Coordination Team to ensure that these are mandatory.
- Furthermore, it has to be noted that the expertise of the NHCPs do not cover all the topics included in PARC; thus, **the requests have to be very clear, and it would be useful to organize short briefings to the NHCPs on certain requests by the corresponding WPLs/TLs**. Furthermore, it should be always clearly stated who should answer the request (e.g. NHCP or NH members). The requests should always include an explanation on what the requested information will be used for.
- **A calendar including all upcoming requests should be created and regularly updated**. This could facilitate the better handling of the requests, e.g. NHCPs could include them in the agenda of the NH meetings. Furthermore, an appropriate time should be provided for the completion of the requests. This should be further discussed and specified (e.g. minimum time interval for completion).

4. Conclusion

Feedback from this first mapping of needs of the NHs is interesting on two levels: not only has it provided valuable insights in the structuring and organization of NHs in the different countries participating in PARC but it has also stimulated discussions and suggestions on how these could be further supported and improved. As seen from the recommendations resulting from the analysis of the input and the importance of the NHs for PARC activities, it is essential for us to implement an efficient two-way dialogue between the different PARC groups and the NHs. The annual surveys mapping the needs of the NHs provide a good tool to collect their input and suggestions. Every year response will therefore enable us to not only highlight and valorize the progress and activities of the NHs but also to reflect on possible improvements both to the process and the way we ask questions or collect input from the NHCPs and the NHs and also to the implementation of potential activities, like capacity building or good practice sharing activities that would support the NHs and their structuring at the national level and thus contribute to the sustainability of PARC's programme and infrastructure on the long term.

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Annex I. First survey for mapping the needs of the National Hubs

This survey is carried out under Task 2.3 ‘Sustainability’. It is sent to all National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) for completion by 31/01/2023.

The National Hubs (NHs) are the national structures which support all PARC activities. There are no prescriptive rules and the construction is based on country needs. However, as a minimum they should include the national PARC partners as well as the national PARC Governing Board member institute(s). Each NH has a NHCP whose responsibility is to i) coordinate the national inputs to PARC either via the National Hub Co-Coordinators (NHCs) or through the WPLs; ii) convene NH meetings and iii) feed the NH needs into PARC. NHs are instrumental for the success of PARC and an indicator on the “performance” will be followed throughout the implementation of PARC.

The aim of this survey is to develop a baseline for the PARC NHs, to respond to specific requests from WPLs and to gather some preliminary information on the needs and expectations of the NHs themselves.

The outcomes of this survey will be used to promote the development of the NHs by transposing the results of this survey into training and capacity building programmes in WP9 ‘Building infrastructural and human capacities’ as well as by developing materials which support the work of the NHCPs. The results will also be used within the scope of the indicators for output, outcome and impact. The mapping of the needs of the NHs will be a living process and will continue the entire duration of the Partnership. Annual general surveys will be sent out and will be complemented by specific surveys on hot topics or requests by WPLs. A calendar of these will be set to enable NHCPs to organize their completion as efficiently as possible. These annual surveys will cover specific needs of the NH in the future.

We ask all NHCPs to complete this survey. Most of the questions are addressed only to the NHCPs; however, there are a couple of questions that require discussions within each NH and a compilation of answers by the NHCPs. These latter ones are marked in the survey. The third section of the survey provides a link to a WP 9-specific survey on training needs, to be distributed to all NH members.

The collected information will be treated confidentially according to the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Data obtained from this survey will be saved and stored by the Portuguese National Institute of Health Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA) during the implementation and up to 5 years after the end of the PARC project. The pseudonymised data will be processed by the Task 2.3 partners and the National Hub Co-Coordinators.

Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey!

If you have any questions, please contact us.

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General information on the NHCP

Your name

Name of your institute

The country that you are representing

Your e-mail address

Section 1: Questions on the structure, operation and the first experiences of the National Hub***To be completed by the NHCP***

1. Have you established a NH in your country?

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide some information on the NH.

1.1. How many organisations are involved in your NH?

open numeric question

1.2. Who is involved in the NH? (*Select all options that apply.*)

- Beneficiaries and Affiliated Entities involved as participants in PARC
- PARC Governing Board member organisations
- Other scientists
- Other policy makers
- Other regulators
- NGOs
- Representatives from industry
- Consumer associations
- Trade unions
- Other stakeholders, please specify: *open text*

1.3. What expertise is covered by the NH members? (*Select all options that apply.*)

- Human biomonitoring
- Environmental and multisource monitoring
- Occupational exposure
- Hazard assessment
- Risk assessment
- FAIR data
- Communication and dissemination
- Other, please specify: *open text*

1.4. Are you planning to expand the NH with other organisations before May 2023?

- Yes
- No

1.5. Is the NH a follow-up of the NH established in the framework of the HBM4EU project?

- Yes
- No

2. To your knowledge, are there any intersectoral groups in your country (including scientists, policy makers, etc.; others than PARC National Hub) which are established to discuss national priorities and activities on chemical risk assessment?

- Yes
- No

2.1. If yes, please provide further information on the group(s).

open text

3. Do you have any difficulties in identifying the potential members of your NH?

- Yes
- No

3.1. If yes, please provide further information on the difficulties you are facing.

open text

4. Do you have any difficulties in engaging any relevant stakeholders?

- Yes
- No
- I have not contacted all potential members yet

4.1. If yes, please indicate the stakeholder(s) you have difficulties in engaging. (*Select all options that apply.*)

- Beneficiaries and Affiliated Entities involved as participants in PARC
- PARC Governing Board member organisations
- Other scientists
- Other policy makers
- Other regulators
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs)
- Representatives from industry
- Consumer associations
- Trade unions
- Other stakeholders, please specify: *open text*

5. What kind of regular actions are you planning to implement as NHCP at national level during the first year of PARC (up to the end of April 2023)? (*Select all options that apply.*)

- Organising NH meeting(s)
- Establishing a NH platform to share documents, etc.
- Sending out newsletters prepared by yourself as NHCP
- Organising any conferences, workshops or seminars
- Preparing communication materials and organising awareness raising campaigns
- Other activity(ies), please specify: *open text*

5.1. Please describe how, in your opinion, the different PARC groups (NHCs, WPL and task co-leaders (TL), etc.) could support the national actions that you would like to implement.

open text

6. How many National Hub meetings are you planning in the first year of PARC (up to the end of April 2023)? Please include the past NH meetings.

- 1
- 2-3
- more than 3

7. Are you planning to invite all NH members to all NH meetings?

- Yes, all members will be invited to each NH meeting
- No, the list of invited partners will depend on the agenda of the meeting

- I do not know

8. Please describe existing or potential problems that you are facing with regard to the organisation of a NH meeting.

open text

9. Several requests to the NHCPs are expected from the different WPLs during the entire duration of the Partnership. All requests will be forwarded by the NHCs.

What kind of approach do you prefer? *(Select all options that apply.)*

- I prefer to receive each request in a separate e-mail.
- I prefer to receive several requests at the same time.
- I would like to know more about the expected requests in advance (e.g., through a calendar available through the PARC SharePoint).

9.1. If you have any suggestions, please shortly describe them.

open text

10. How are you planning to collect inputs from the NH members for requests from the different WPLs that require input by all NH members? *(Select all options that apply.)*

- Contacting the relevant members directly
- Forwarding the request to all NH members
- Organising a NH meeting
- Trying to answer the request myself without contacting the NH members
- Other, please specify: *open text*

11. Do you have any suggestion on how the NHCs can support the steering of the National Hubs (e.g., list of proposed topics to be discussed, coordinate requests from WP Leaders)?

- Yes
- No

11.1. If yes, please describe your suggestion.

open text

12. The members of the NH might also formulate some requests towards the NHCPs. Please describe here if you have already received specific requests from your NH members and for which you feel that the support of the NHCs, WPLs &/or Coordination Team is needed.

open text

Section 2: Topic specific questions

To be discussed and compiled for the NH by the NHCP

Questions on communication activities

1. Are you planning to create a dedicated section about PARC on the website of your (NHCP) or other NH members' institute? *(Select all options that apply.)*

- Yes, my institute will have a dedicated section about PARC
- Yes, other institutes in the NH will have a dedicated section about PARC on their website
- No, but news related to PARC will be shared on the website of either my institute or other institutes in the NH
- I do not know

2. PARC will develop and disseminate several communication products (e.g., leaflets, policy briefs, research briefs, factsheets, infographics, videos, newsletters).

Which communication material should be translated in national languages?

open text

3. Are you willing to translate communication materials (if PMs are allocated)?

- Yes
- No

Question on the sustainability of the PARC-related activities

Task 2.3 is responsible, among others, for framing the exit strategy. As a first step, Task 2.3 would like to identify those activities that are already sustainable at national level. Please consult the answers with the National Hub members.

1. Which activities are sustainable in your country? *(Select all options that apply.)*

- Human biomonitoring
(e.g. national funding is available to regularly conduct national human biomonitoring studies targeting different age groups and substances)
- Environmental monitoring (not already available)
(e.g. national funding is available to regularly conduct environmental monitoring studies targeting non-regulated substances)
- Non-targeted screening
(e.g. national funding is available to regularly develop and apply non-targeted screening approaches in different fields /e.g. environmental monitoring or human biomonitoring/)
- Toxicology: NAM development
(e.g., national funding is available to regularly conduct toxicological studies /NAM development)
- Computational toxicology
(e.g. national funding is available to regularly conduct computational toxicological studies)
- Toolbox and models enabling the application of a safe and sustainable by design (SSBD) approach
(e.g. national funding is available to develop and apply toolboxes and models for the application of SSBD approach)
- Prioritisation process for substances
(e.g. a well-established process exists for the identification of priority substances)
- Capacity for data storage
(e.g. the storage of the different national databases related to chemicals is well-managed and resources to continuously maintain their storage are available)
- Access to data (environmental, human biomonitoring, etc.)
(e.g. FAIR data principles are applied for national databases)
- Other chemical data flows, please specify: *open text*

The question of sustainability of PARC activities and our exit strategy is crucial and must be discussed in the different PARC groups from the start and in particular with the Governing Board members. Please note that a separate survey will be launched in February 2023, which will contain more questions and suggestions for discussion on the sustainability of PARC activities at European level.

Section 3: WP-specific surveys

First PARC's Training Needs Survey

All NH members should be asked to complete this survey

Task 9.4 'Training' is responsible for i) mapping training needs, ii) collecting and compiling training opportunities, and iii) providing support for the organisation of training.

To capture training needs in PARC-related scientific topics, Task 9.4 is now distributing among PARC participants, stakeholders and NHs the first PARC's Training Needs Survey. The survey is available here: <https://survey-insa.min-saude.pt/redcap/surveys/?s=HHAMXKJXNW>

We would like to ask you to complete the survey for your organization as well as to distribute the survey among the NH members.

The deadline for completion of the survey on training needs: 6th February 2023

Thank you for completing the survey!